

CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIVEMENT

this cetificate is proudly presented to

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Mamatova Matluba Abduxalilovna

**YUQUMLI KASALLIKARNING TARQALISHIDA MIKROORGANIZIMLARNING
RO'LI - QONDA HIMOYA FUNKSIYASINING SHAKILLANISHI**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

OKTABR/ 2022

